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Effect of E-beam sanitation of surface mould cheese on texture and sensory attributes

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1 **Effect of E-beam sanitation of surface mould cheese on texture and sensory**
2 **attributes**

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23

24 **Abstract**

25

26 The effects of E-beam radiation at doses up to 3 kGy on mechanical and colorimetric
27 parameters and sensory attributes of Camembert and Brie cheeses and their behaviour
28 during storage at 4 and 14°C were studied using response surface methodology.
29 Immediately after treatment, no significant differences ($p>0.05$) in adhesiveness,
30 springiness and chewiness were found in either of the cheeses. However, hardness,
31 cohesiveness, gumminess and breaking force decreased in Camembert cheese as the
32 dose increased, while values for the Brie samples remained fairly constant.
33 Nevertheless, no significant differences ($p>0.05$) between untreated and treated
34 samples after two weeks of storage were detected. Minor changes in the colour
35 parameters were due to the E-beam treatment even at 3 kGy and then minimized
36 during storage. A similar behaviour was observed in sensorial parameters. Because
37 the dose studied was higher than that required to achieve the food safety objective
38 according to EU and USA regulations, it was concluded that E-beam treatment is a
39 useful method for sanitizing soft mould-ripening cheeses with negligible changes in the
40 sensory quality and rheological properties.

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42

43 **Keywords:** soft mould-ripened cheese, E-beam radiation, sensory quality, textural
44 attributes, response surface methodology.

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46

47 1. Introduction

48

49 In the dairy industry, cheeses have become predominant consumer goods for a large
50 proportion of the population and their production has emerged as one of the most
51 important activities in this sector. Indeed, more than a third of US milk production is
52 used for cheese manufacture (IDFA, 2010). However, the hygienic status of some
53 cheeses can sometimes be threatened by the contamination of food-borne pathogens,
54 of which *Listeria monocytogenes* has been reported to be of the most concern in soft
55 mould-ripened cheeses (CDC, 2013; EFSA, 2015). Since irradiation technology is an
56 effective method for inactivating pathogens in food, as previously demonstrated in meat
57 products (Zhu et al., 2005), we explored the possibility of using E-beam radiation at
58 doses lower than 3 kGy for the sanitation of Camembert and Brie cheese varieties with
59 successful results (Velasco et al., 2015).

60 However, the radiation of dairy products has often been considered as an inappropriate
61 technique since it can lead to the development of undesirable off-flavours after
62 treatment (Arvanitoyannis & Tserkezou, 2010). Probably for this reason, few papers
63 can be found in the literature on the radiation of dairy products and all of them report
64 that this technology gives rise to both off-odours and off-flavours. For example,
65 chocolate ice cream irradiated at 4 kGy presented an unpleasant (mainly rancid) taste
66 (Adeil Pietranera et al., 2003); vanilla ice cream at doses above 3 kGy showed
67 unfavourable changes in flavour and taste (Kim et al., 2008); thiobarbituric acid-values
68 increased in irradiated Cheddar cheese at 4 kGy (Seisa et al., 2004), which could
69 indicate the acceleration of oxidation phenomena. Nevertheless, it seems that lower
70 radiation doses than those mentioned above do not affect the composition of several
71 cheese products (Konteles et al., 2009; Seisa et al., 2004). In a previous work, it has
72 recently been reported that the absorbed doses required to meet the food safety
73 objective (FSO) according to EU and USDA criteria for *L. monocytogenes* were 1.27
74 and 2.59 kGy, respectively. The bacterial load, mainly of lactic acid bacteria, was

75 reduced by the treatment but injured cells were recovered during storage at 14°C.
76 Moreover, the radiation treatment gave rise to negligible changes in the pH and water
77 activity at doses required to achieve microbial safety (Velasco et al., 2015). Therefore,
78 the objective of this study was to evaluate the texture and sensory changes of
79 Camembert and Brie cheeses stored at 4 and 14°C after E-beam application in order to
80 confirm the suitability of this technology for sanitizing these cheese varieties at doses
81 up to 3 kGy.

82

83 **2. Material and methods**

84

85 **2.1. Sample preparation and irradiation treatment**

86

87 Brie and Camembert cheeses made from pasteurized milk, acquired at a local
88 supermarket, were divided in portions (about 30 g). Then, samples were vacuum-
89 packaged (2 cm of thickness) in 20x20 cm laminated film bags of low gas permeability
90 (oxygen transmission rate of 35 cm³/24h·m²·bar and 150 cm³/24h·m²·bar to carbon
91 dioxide) until vacuum reached 20 kPa. Once the samples were ready, they were
92 treated in the irradiation plant (IONISOS IBERICA, S.A., Tarancón, Spain) under an
93 electron beam radiation source, which operates at 10 MeV. The radiation doses
94 employed were between 1 to 3 kGy. The dose absorbed by samples was checked by
95 determining the absorbance of cellulose triacetate dosimeters (ASTM, 2000)
96 simultaneously irradiated with samples. Experiments were carried out in triplicate at
97 room temperature (18–20°C). The product temperature increased less than 2°C during
98 treatment. Following the treatment, samples were transferred to the laboratory where
99 analyses corresponding to day 0 were performed. The remaining samples were stored
100 at 4.0±0.5 °C and 14.0±0.2 °C (the latter as an example of temperature abuse) to study
101 the behaviour of selected characteristics over time.

102

103 **2.2. Texture analysis**

104

105 The effect of E-beam radiation on the texture of cheeses and how it changes during
106 storage were examined through a puncture test and a texture profile analysis (TPA).
107 Both analyses were carried out at 25°C using a TA.X T2i SMS Stable Micro Systems
108 Texture Analyser (Stable Microsystems Ltd., Surrey, England) with the Texture Expert
109 program. Cheeses were sampled on day 0, 15 (two weeks) and 42 days (six weeks) of
110 storage at 4 and 14°C, using five samples in each analysis. The puncture test, used to
111 examine the breaking force, was conducted as reported elsewhere (Herrero et al.,
112 2009) in cheese rind and core aliquots separately. To obtain both samples, a scalpel
113 was introduced into the area of colour change and the rind was removed from the core.
114 The TPA was carried out in complete samples (core and ring together) according to
115 Velasco et al. (2011), and hardness, springiness, adhesiveness, cohesiveness,
116 gumminess and chewiness parameters were calculated.

117

118 **2.3. Colour analysis**

119

120 Colour determination was conducted as reported in previous research (Velasco et al.,
121 2011), just after the sample radiation and past three weeks of storage at 4 and
122 14°C. Three portions of both cheese types were used for each E-beam treatment (0-3
123 kGy). The L^* (lightness), a^* (redness) and b^* (yellowness) parameters were measured
124 ten times on the sample surface at periods of 0, 4, and 24 h after opening the pack (air
125 exposure time, AET).

126

127 **2.4. Sensory analysis**

128

129 A triangular test, performed as described by Velasco et al. (2011), was carried out at
130 different days during storage at both temperatures (4 and 14°C) to study the behaviour

131 of appearance, flavour and odour of samples treated at 0, 1, 2 and 3 kGy. In addition,
132 panellists were asked to justify their answer with brief descriptions.

133

134 **2.5. Experimental design and Statistical analysis**

135

136 Experimental design and statistical analysis was carried out using a Statgraphics
137 Centurion XVI for Windows (Statistical Graphics Corporation, Rockville, MD, USA). The
138 experimental units corresponded to the individual cheese portion (about 30 g). The
139 effects of the E-beam treatment (four levels: 0, 1, 2 and 3 kGy), the storage
140 temperature (two levels: 4 and 14°C) and storage time [three levels for texture analysis
141 (0, 2 and 6 weeks) and two levels for colour and sensory analysis (0 and 3 weeks)] on
142 the textural and sensory properties of Camembert and Brie cheeses were analysed by
143 employing a factorial experimental design [(4 x 2 x3 (for texture) or 4x2x2 (for sensory
144 analysis)]. The data were analysed by means of a model for three-way factorial analysis
145 for textural and sensory parameters:

$$146 \quad Y_{ijk} = \mu + A_i + B_j + (AB)_{ij} + C_k + (AC)_{ik} + (BC)_{jk} + (ABC)_{ijk} + \varepsilon_{ijk} \quad (1)$$

147 Where Y is the data observed, μ is the general mean, A , B , C and their combinations
148 are the main effects and ε is the residual error.

149 In the case of colour analysis, in addition to factors already mentioned the influence of
150 AET was also studied (three levels: 0, 4 and 24 hours).

151 The combinations of the variables or factors (E-beam treatment, temperature and time
152 of storage, AET) were replicated in triplicate.

153 After checking the goodness of fit of the texture and colour analysis data to a normal
154 distribution (90% confidence) using the Shapiro-Wilks test, simultaneous effects
155 produced by the factors or their combinations (E-beam treatment, temperature and
156 time storage and AET) on binding textural and colour parameters of both cheeses
157 studied were analyzed.

158 MANOVA tests were conducted to determine if mentioned effects were significant
 159 (Wilk's lambda p -value <0.05) on the whole TPA parameters or colour parameters,
 160 since they are measured simultaneously in each TPA or colour analysis assay. In
 161 affirmative cases, multifactor ANOVA were performed with data of each parameter to
 162 determine which effects were significant ($p<0.05$). In Puncture Test analysis, only the
 163 multifactor ANOVA was carried out after the Shapiro-Wilks test.

164 To describe the effects of both E-beam radiation and storage on textural and colour
 165 parameters, surface models were obtained by a regression analysis to estimate the
 166 response function as is shown below:

$$167 \quad Y = \beta_0 + \sum \beta_i X_i + \sum \beta_{ii} X_i^2 + \sum \beta_{ij} X_i X_j \quad (2)$$

168 where Y is the predicted response (estimated texture and colour parameters), β_0 , β_i , β_{ii}
 169 and β_{ij} are the coefficients estimated from regression. They represent the linear,
 170 quadratic and cross-product effects of applied dose (X_1), storage time (X_2), storage
 171 temperature (X_3) and, in the colour analysis, AET (X_4) on the response.

172 ANOVA was applied to test the statistical significance of each factor introduced in the
 173 model and non-significant factors, with a confidence level of 95% ($p>0.05$), were
 174 gradually eliminated.

175 In order to check the goodness of fit of models, Root Mean Square Error (RMSE) was
 176 also calculated by using 30 randomly selected data from experimental units treated and
 177 stored at the different levels described above according to the following equation:

$$178 \quad RMSE = \sqrt{(1/n) \sum (Y - Y_{obs})^2} \quad (3)$$

179 where Y is the predicted data, Y_{obs} the result obtained in the experimental analyses and
 180 n the number of samples.

181 To establish the significance level of the triangular test results, the tables of the
 182 minimum number of panellists with correct answers were used (Pedrero & Pangborn,
 183 1989).

184

185 3. Results and discussion

186

187 **3.1. Texture analysis**

188

189 Table 1 shows the combined effect of E-beam treatment and storage conditions (time
190 and temperature) on textural attributes of Camembert and Brie cheeses. The
191 multifactor ANOVA results indicated significant interactions ($p < 0.05$) between doses
192 and storage time and/or temperature in the case of the rind and core BF (Table 1) and
193 hardness, cohesiveness and gumminess (data not shown). Therefore, the impact of the
194 E-beam treatment on the above rheological parameters was affected by the storage
195 conditions (mainly by the storage time). A complete second-order polynomial model
196 was used to evaluate the relationship between the interaction effect of E-beam and
197 storage conditions on textural attributes of both cheeses. Core BF and cohesiveness
198 models which presented a lower goodness of fit ($R^2_{adj} < 0.85$) were discarded.
199 Therefore, Table 2 only shows the significant ($p < 0.05$) regression coefficients of
200 models with R^2_{adj} between 0.86 and 0.96 (rind BF, hardness and gumminess). To
201 determine differences between predicted values and observed values, the RMSE was
202 calculated for rind BF, hardness and gumminess models of both cheese samples
203 (Table 2). The results confirmed acceptable goodness of fit of the models.

204 For a better understanding of the combined effects, the estimated response surfaces
205 for rind BF of both cheeses are shown in Figure 1. In this figure, it can be observed that
206 the higher the dose, the lower the BF ($p < 0.05$) immediately after treatment. The
207 experimental rind values for this parameter achieved an average value of 4.50 ± 0.50 N
208 and 4.60 ± 0.42 N for untreated Camembert and Brie cheese respectively while values
209 for samples treated at 3 kGy were 2.47 ± 0.31 N (Camembert) and 3.17 ± 0.24 N (Brie).
210 During the first three weeks of storage, the rind BF dropped sharply particularly in the
211 case of non-irradiated cheeses stored at 4°C (from 4.50 ± 0.50 N to 0.43 ± 0.88 N and
212 from 4.60 ± 0.42 N to 0.42 ± 0.11 N in Camembert and Brie, respectively). In general, at

213 the end of storage (six weeks), the BF of control samples were significantly lower
214 ($p<0.05$) than those exhibited by irradiated rinds.

215 On the other hand, the BF behaviour of the cores in both cheeses showed a similar
216 trend. In general, the BF of the cores diminished gradually during storage. However,
217 and depending of the dose applied, the values of non-irradiated samples from
218 Camembert cheese were significantly lower ($p<0.05$) after six weeks (data not shown).
219 Regarding the interaction between dose and storage time (Table 1 and Figure 1),
220 radiation seems to attenuate the loss of resistance to penetration of the cheeses during
221 storage.

222 A combination of the structural differences between rinds and cores and the effect of
223 radiation on enzymes could explain these findings. Hence, the results from day 0 seem
224 to confirm the work of Ham et al. (2009), who reported that the amount of α_{S1} -casein in
225 “Queso Blanco” cheese subjected to gamma irradiation decreased proportionally with
226 the dose applied. Likewise, Seisa et al. (2004) postulated that differences in the
227 development of the peptide profile of irradiated Cheddar cheese are due, in part, to
228 protein degradation by radiation. Regarding the faster decrease in the rinds BF during
229 storage Guizani et al. (2002) reported that the lipolytic and proteolytic activities of
230 fungal enzymes in the rind are about twice the intensity of those occurring in the paste
231 since the mould concentration is higher on the surface than inside. In addition, the
232 cushioning effect of E-beam irradiation observed during storage might be due to two
233 different mechanisms. On the one hand, there could be less proteolysis in treated
234 samples due to changes in either the protein conformation of enzymes or substrates
235 induced by radicals from water radiolysis, which might have an inhibitory effect until
236 these radicals are recombined to form water molecules again (Seisa et al., 2004). The
237 second possibility, it may be due to the cross-linking of caseinates derived from
238 radiation, which is favoured by the presence of calcium (Kuan et al., 2013).

239 In Figure 2, the effects of E-beam treatment and storage time at 4 °C on TPA
240 parameters are shown. Similar results were observed in both cheeses when stored at

241 14°C (data not shown). No significant differences ($p>0.05$) attributable to E-beam
242 treatment in adhesiveness, springiness and chewiness of both cheeses were found
243 (data not shown). In the Brie cheese, just after treatment, no effects on hardness were
244 observed for non-irradiated (17.68 ± 0.82 N) and treated samples even when 3 kGy
245 (17.71 ± 0.8 N) were applied. However, a minor, but significant ($p<0.05$), influence of the
246 dose was appreciated in the Camembert cheese (27.96 ± 1.00 N vs. 21.25 ± 1.80 N). It
247 can be concluded that, in general, the application of E-beam had barely any effect on
248 the hardness. During storage at both temperatures, a significant softening ($p<0.05$)
249 was observed, which was more pronounced in the Camembert cheese. This finding
250 confirms those observed in the puncture test, since the outer surface layer (the rind) is
251 the first structure that makes contact with the probe when the analysis is performed. A
252 softening by radiation has been recorded previously in cheese slices (Velasco et al.,
253 2011) while other authors did not observe textural differences between radiated and
254 untreated cheeses in some varieties, such as Feta (Konteles et al., 2009) and smear-
255 ripened (Ennahar et al., 1994) cheeses. The gumminess (Figure 2) of both cheeses
256 displayed a similar pattern to that of the hardness although the absolute data were
257 certainly different. For cohesiveness (data not shown) the lowest values ($p<0.05$) were
258 recorded in Camembert samples subjected to higher doses (2 and 3 kGy). During the
259 first third of storage time, this parameter remained fairly constant, but later a decrease
260 was observed, which was dependent on the interaction dose-storage time ($p<0.005$)
261 and time-temperature of storage ($p<0.0005$), in such a way that samples (control and
262 treated) stored at the same temperature showed similar values ($p>0.05$) of
263 cohesiveness after two weeks of storage, with higher values being recorded in samples
264 stored at 4°C (0.35 ± 0.04 N) than those kept at 14°C (0.15 ± 0.03 N). In summary, it
265 could be concluded that E-beam treatment has a minor effect on these rheological
266 parameters (at least a dose lower than 3 kGy) which can barely be detected by
267 consumers.

268 Several authors (Spinnler & Gripon, 2004) reported that textural changes of
269 Camembert cheeses during ripening are due to calcium migration in response to the
270 pH gradient and to the activities of fungal and rennet enzymes. Calcium phosphate
271 precipitates at the typically high pH of these cheese rinds. Then, the calcium of the
272 core migrates to the surface to restore the equilibrium, causing a destabilization of the
273 micelles and a consequent softening of the cheese (McSweeney, 2004). The changes
274 observed in the texture of the untreated and treated samples could be related to this
275 phenomenon.

276

277 **3.2. Colour analysis**

278

279 3.2.1. Effect of E-beam treatment and storage conditions on the cheese rind

280

281 The colour parameters of samples were also determined in core and rind portions.
282 Analyses were performed immediately following E-beam treatment (day 0) and after
283 three weeks of storage at 4 °C or 14°C. Measurements were made immediately after
284 opening the vacuum package and after the exposure to air for 4 and 24 hours. The
285 MANOVA results (Table 3) showed significant interactions ($p<0.05$) between the
286 effects of the selected factors (E-beam treatment, time and temperature and air
287 exposure time (AET)). Therefore, the effect of the radiation was also dependent on the
288 storage conditions, which seems to confirm the results previously found in other
289 irradiated foods, namely fresh pork loin (García-Márquez et al., 2012).

290 As the results in both temperatures were similar, data for 4°C were only presented in
291 Figure 3. In this figure, the effects of the selected factors on the lightness (L^*), redness
292 (a^*) and yellowness (b^*) of rind are shown. The respective regression equations were
293 shown in the supplementary data (Table S1). The most remarkable effect of E-beam
294 alone (day 0, AET 0 hours) was the elevation ($p<0.05$) in these parameters as the
295 radiation dose increased. The increase in lightness was also observed in irradiated

296 Anthotyros cheese (Tsiotsias et al., 2002), although no changes were detected in
297 conventional cheese slices (Velasco et al., 2011) and even a decrease in this
298 parameter due to radiation treatment was reported in sliced and pizza cheeses (Kim et
299 al., 2010) and Feta cheese (Konteles et al., 2009). Likewise, the oxidation of pigments
300 by exposure to light has been considered to possibly explain the higher redness of
301 Havarti (Kristensen et al., 2000) and semi-hard (Juric et al., 2003) cheeses.

302 However, the effect of AET was noticeable. Briefly, it can be said (Figure 3),

- 303 • A fairly similar trend was observed at both storage temperatures.
- 304 • The lightness continuously decreased as AET elapsed but the higher the radiation
305 dose the lower the decrease, which was clearer in Camembert cheese.
- 306 • In Brie cheese, the redness values remained quite constant during AET but those of
307 the Camembert were clearly higher as the radiation dose increased either
308 decreasing later when samples were stored at 4°C or remaining at the same level at
309 14°C (data not shown).
- 310 • The yellowness suffered a slight increase in the Camembert cheese during the first
311 half of the AET to be restored afterwards. The same pattern was observed in Brie
312 when the dose applied was 3 kGy but, at lower doses, an increase during the AET
313 was produced reaching the same level as samples treated at 3 kGy after 20 hours of
314 exposure to air.

315

316 3.2.2. Effect of E-beam treatment and storage conditions on the cheese core

317

318 Figure 4 shows the response surface plots for the effects on the core colour
319 parameters (L^* , a^* and b^*) of dose and AET in different times of storage at 4°C. These
320 parameters showed a similar trend in both cheeses although either values were slightly
321 different between cheeses [e.g. the average value for L^* figures at day 0 after opening
322 the package were 87.64 ± 2.05 for Camembert and 88.22 ± 1.93 for Brie] or, in some
323 cases, significant effects were observed [e.g. similar a^* values (-3.44 ± 0.14 ; $p > 0.05$)

324 immediately after the package opening (Figure 4, day 0) were observed in Camembert
325 cheese (untreated and treated) while in Brie (Figure 4, day 0) a significant increase (-
326 4.55 ± 0.24 to -3.07 ± 0.16 ; $p < 0.05$) was found]. Accordingly, the effects of the selected
327 factors in this study on the colour parameters of both cheeses may be summarized as
328 follows:

- 329 • The E-beam treatment had very little effect on the lightness (L^*). No significant
330 changes ($p > 0.05$) in this parameter were due to the E-beam radiation (Figure 4, day
331 0) but a decrease was produced later during the AET, which was more marked at
332 14°C mainly in the Camembert cheese (data not shown). In both cheeses, an
333 inverse relationship between the decreasing intensity in L^* values and the doses
334 was detected. The increase in lightness by the radiation may be related to a slight
335 syneresis of the cheese mass by the treatment followed by a gradual release of fat,
336 which could result in an increase in L^* values although it has also been attributed to
337 the water expelled to the surface from the cheese body (Tsiotsias et al., 2002).
- 338 • A decrease in the first half of AET was noticed in the redness (a^*) to be almost
339 restored to initial values afterwards. This behaviour was less balanced in the Brie
340 variety since the values showed greater variations.
- 341 • An opposite effect to the redness was observed in the yellowness (b^*), i.e. an
342 increase in the first half of AET to diminish over the next few hours. No important
343 differences were observed between the storage temperatures.

344

345 3.3. Sensory analysis

346

347 The impact of irradiation dose on the sensory aspects of cheeses is shown in Table 4.
348 A triangular test was carried out immediately after E-beam treatment (day 0) and after
349 3 weeks of storage at 4 and 14°C to check their stability over time. The objective of this
350 study was to determine the dose to be applied to sanitize the surface mould ripened
351 cheeses without significantly changing in the sensory attributes. Therefore, the

352 experiments were performed to compare non-irradiated samples with samples E-beam
353 treated at 1, 2 and 3 kGy. For this reason, differences between doses are not
354 described.

355 Although minor changes in the colour of both cheeses were instrumentally detected, no
356 significant differences ($p>0.05$) in the appearance were observed by the panellists in
357 the triangular test at day 0 and also after three weeks of storage. These results are in
358 agreement with those reported in Camembert (Chincholle, 1991), Feta (Konteles et al.,
359 2009) and Karish (Aly et al., 2012) cheeses treated with the different dose (from 2.5 to
360 5 kGy).

361 In relation to the odour and flavour (Table 4), panellists found significant differences
362 ($p<0.05$) between treated and untreated samples immediately after the E-beam
363 radiation, which were justified by a slight aroma and a taste of burnt plastic, muddy or
364 metallic notes in radiated samples, even at doses of 1 kGy. This treatment effect
365 diminished during storage and, after three weeks, only significant differences ($p<0.05$)
366 could be detected between the controls and samples E-beam treated at 3 kGy in both
367 cheeses. These results were observed in the samples stored at both storage
368 temperatures (4 and 14°C). Several authors have described the reversibility of sensory
369 changes caused by radiation in different varieties of cheese (Konteles et al., 2009;
370 Tsiotsias et al, 2002; Velasco et al., 2011). Hence, Seisa et al. (2004) matched the
371 pungent taste detected just after treatment in irradiated Cheddar cheese with the
372 presence of hydroxyl radicals, which decline progressively. Furthermore, it is likely that
373 the effects due to radiation could be overlapped by sapid substances derived from the
374 metabolism of *P. camemberti*, which, in turn, gives rise to a uniformity of both odour
375 and flavour of samples. In this sense, it is well known that the ammonia concentration
376 over storage increases even at refrigeration temperatures, as has been repeatedly
377 reported previously (Gripon, 1997). Detectable flavour changes, described as burnt or
378 musty, have also been reported (Jones & Jelen, 1998) in Camembert cheese when 0.3
379 kGy were applied. However, Chincholle (1991) found no significant changes in the

380 flavour of Camembert cheese (made from raw milk) irradiated with doses up to 2.5
381 kGy.

382 The preservation of the appearance of non-irradiated cheese is essential from a market
383 perspective because consumer choice is based on the first perceived attribute,
384 especially in products packaged in transparent films. In the case of radiated cheeses, it
385 seems that the odour and flavour of irradiated samples are practically restored during
386 storage time, at least when doses lower than 3 kGy have been used. Therefore,
387 sensorial differences with the non-treated cheeses would become negligible. Although
388 slight changes in irradiated samples have been detected, it is necessary to bear in
389 mind that *P. camemberti* is endowed with powerful enzyme activities (Cerning et al.,
390 1987) causing pronounced changes in the appearance, odour and flavour of cheeses
391 during the ripening process to the point that great sensorial differences are observed
392 between cheeses from the same variety produced by different brands and even from
393 the same manufacturer depending on the time of ripening. It is, therefore, possible that
394 sensory differences between conventional cheeses could be of greater magnitude than
395 those described in the present work for E-beam treated samples and their controls.
396 Therefore, consumers may hardly detect the slight sensorial changes caused by the
397 radiation at doses necessary to guarantee the safety in relation to *L. monocytogenes*.

398

399

400 **4. Conclusions**

401

402 In general, the effect of E-beam radiation at doses up to 3 kGy on the texture and
403 colour parameters gave rise to minimal changes, which are attenuated during storage.

404 The minor changes in sensory characteristics detected in treated samples diminished
405 during storage in such a way that after three weeks no significant differences between
406 untreated and treated samples at doses even at 2 kGy were noticed by panellists.

407

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409

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414

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508 **Figure captions**

509

510 Figure 1. Effect of dose radiation (0–3 kGy) and storage time at 4°C (grey) and 14°C
511 (black) on the breaking force (BF) of the rind from Camembert and Brie cheeses.

512

513 Figure 2. Selected Texture profile analysis (TPA) parameters of Camembert (grey) and
514 Brie (black) cheeses affected by E-beam treatment (0–3 kGy) and storage time at
515 4°C.

516

517 Figure 3. Combined effect of dose radiation and exposure time to air on lightness (L^*),
518 redness (a^*) and yellowness (b^*) of Camembert (grey) and Brie (black) rind at
519 different times of storage at 4 °C.

520

521 The respective regression equations were shown in the supplementary material (Table
522 S1).

523

524 Figure 4. Combined effect of dose radiation and exposure time to air on lightness (L^*),
525 redness (a^*) and yellowness (b^*) of Camembert (grey) and Brie (black) core at
526 different times of storage at 4 °C.

527

528 The respective regression equations were shown in the supplementary material (Table
529 S1).

Table 1. Effect of the storage conditions (time and temperature) and the E-beam treatment on the textural features (the puncture test breaking force and TPA parameters) of Camembert and Brie cheeses

Cheese	Rind Breaking Force ^a	Core Breaking Force ^a	TPA ^b
Camembert	T x time ***	D x T x time *	T x time ***
	D x time ***		D x time ***
Brie	T x time *	D x time **	T x time ***
	D x time ***		D x time **

Factors: time, T and D denote storage time (day), storage temperature (°C) and E-beam treatment dose (kGy), respectively.

^a Multifactor ANOVA p-value: *** p<0.0005; ** p<0.005; * p<0.05

^b MANOVA Lambda Wilk's p-value: *** p<0.0005; ** p<0.005; * p<0.05

Table 2. Coefficients ($p < 0.05$) and goodness of fit (R^2 and RMSE) of Response Surface Models of selected textural attributes of Camembert (C) and Brie (B) cheeses

		Rind Breaking Force	Hardness	Gumminess
R^2 adjusted	C	0.89	0.94	0.89
	B	0.96	0.96	0.90
RMSE	C	0.48	2.16	1.32
	B	0.33	0.95	0.68
Constant	C	4.10	25,18	12.86
	B	4.28	17.33	6.57
Linear effects				
D^a	C	-0.457	-0,95	-1.41
	B	-0.316	--	0.39
time	C	-0.268	-1,49	-0.64
	B	-0.323	-0,63	-0.15
T	C	--	--	-0.11
	B	--	--	--
Quadratic effects				
$(D)^2$	C	--	--	--
	B	--	--	--
$(\text{time})^2$	C	0.004	0,023	0.009
	B	0.005	0,010	0.002
$(T)^2$	C	--	--	--
	B	--	--	--
Cross-product effects				
D · time	C	0.015	0,051	0.051
	B	0.010	--	-0.016
D · T	C	--	--	--
	B	--	--	--
time · T	C	--	-0,005	--
	B	--	-0,003	-0.002
D · time · T	C	--	--	--
	B	--	--	--

^a Factors: D, time and T denote E-beam treatment dose (kGy), storage time (day), and storage temperature (°C), respectively.

Table 3. Influence of the storage factors (time and temperature), the exposure to air and the E-beam treatment on the CIELab colour parameters of Camembert and Brie cheeses.

	Camembert	Brie
Rind	time x AET *** T x time ***	time x AET x D *** T x time ***
Core	T x time x D * T x time x AET *	T x time x D *** AET x D *

Factors: AET, time, T and D denote air exposure time (hours), storage time (day), storage temperature (°C) and E-beam treatment dose (kGy), respectively.

Significance (MANOVA Lambda Wilk's p-value): *** $p < 0.0005$; ** $p < 0.005$; * $p < 0.05$

Table 4. Sensory characteristics of untreated and irradiated Camembert (C) and Brie (B) cheese that showed significant differences ($p < 0.05$) in the triangular test after treatment (day 0) and elapsed three weeks of storage at 4 or 14 °C.

	Storage conditions		
	Day 0	4°C (3 weeks)	14°C (3 weeks)
0 vs. 1 kGy	O _{C,B} - F _{C,B}		
0 vs. 2 kGy	O _{C,B} - F _{C,B}		
0 vs. 3 kGy	O _{C,B} - F _{C,B}	O _{C,B} - F _{C,B}	O _{C,B} - F _{C,B}

A, O, F: Significant differences ($P < 0.05$) for appearance, odour and flavour respectively

Figure 1

FIGURE 2

FIGURE 3

FIGURE 4

Highlights:

- Textural and colour aspects of cheeses are mainly affected by storage conditions
- Radiation seems to attenuate cheese softening during storage
- Colour changes produced by dose are not noticeable compared to those of air exposure
- Effects of dose up to 3 kGy on sensory aspects become negligible during storage